

Replicability Study on Reliability Prediction for Health-Related Content

LUKA BENZIA / 11778695, Technical University of Vienna, Austria

PHILIP LISZT / 1227444, Technical University of Vienna, Austria

TANJA NEUHERZ / 01501766, Technical University of Vienna, Austria

NIELS VAN SLOOTEN / 12302673, Technical University of Vienna, Austria

In this replication experiment, we examined the replicability of the study by Fernández-Pichel et al. on the prediction of the reliability of health-related content. In the replication, the experimental design, procedures and analyses described in the original paper were reproduced as closely as possible. Despite difficulties, such as unavailable hardware, our results are consistent with and confirm those of the original study.

1 INTRODUCTION

Scientific knowledge relies on the foundation of replicability, which ensures that experimental results can be independently verified and validated. In this report, we present a comprehensive investigation of the replicability of the research study entitled "Replicability Study on Reliability Prediction for Health-Related Content" [1].

This investigation aims to replicate the experimental design, procedures and results described in the paper and to highlight the challenges and difficulties encountered during the replication process.

The selected paper addresses the challenge of assessing the reliability of online health-related content, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. By replicating the Sondhi et al. [4] study with their own code, the researchers confirm the robustness of the original results by reporting comparable performance and validating the conclusions. The study extends its impact by evaluating the prediction technology using new datasets [3] [2]. Our report walks through the experimental strategy described in the paper and attempts to faithfully replicate each step and assess the reproducibility of the reported results.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Experimental Setup

Original Experimental Setup:

In the original study, a vector support machine (SVM) was employed as the learning method, utilizing a C++ implementation. For compatibility, the researchers used the SVMlight Python wrapper, transforming the problem into a two-class classification task. The evaluation utilized 5-fold cross-validation, with a weighted accuracy metric (λ) employed for performance assessment. Three variants of λ were considered (1, 2, 3), and the SVM classifier was tuned by adjusting the cost-factor to λ during training.

Experiments were conducted on an Ubuntu 19.04 machine with 32 GB RAM, 240 GB storage, and an Intel Core i7-9750H CPU @ 2.60 GHz. Python 3.7.3 in an Anaconda 4.8.0 environment was used. For CLEF eHealth dataset experiments, a CentOS 7.6.1810 server with 377 GB RAM, 15T storage, and Intel Xeon CPU E5-2630 v4 processor was necessary.

Our Experimental Setup:

Authors' addresses: Luka Benzia / 11778695, Technical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria; Philip Liszt / 1227444, Technical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria; Tanja Neuherz / 01501766, Technical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria; Niels van Slooten / 12302673, Technical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria.

In our replication, we utilized the Git repository¹ from the original study with a `build.sh` script and `requirements.txt`. The experiments were conducted on a Microsoft Azure Virtual Machine with 16 GB of RAM, using the Standard D4s v3 configuration with 4 vCPUs. The Virtual Machine ran on Ubuntu 20.04.

It is important to note that our choices were constrained by limited access to the specific hardware and software mentioned in the original study, yet we have endeavored to replicate the conditions as closely as possible within the resources available to us.

2.2 Data and Features

Original study:

Sondhi et al. manually created a fully balanced dataset with reliable and unreliable websites. This dataset was made available by Fernández-Pichel et al. in their Git repository. Positive instances were randomly selected from HON2-accredited websites, while negative instances were intentionally sought through strategic web searches using queries such as disease name + "miracle cure." The authors conducted a thematic analysis to avoid topic-related classification. They extracted keywords related to diseases present on reliable sites and manually created search queries for unreliable sites.

As the study expanded, datasets from Schwarz et al. and CLEF were also examined and evaluated using the same methodology. Two of the datasets were part of the Git repository and thus matched the data sources of the original study. However, the CLEF dataset, linked in the Git repository due to its substantial size (96 GB), could not be evaluated due to computational limitations.

Replication effort:

For our replication, we accessed the data available in the provided Git repository¹, mirroring the dataset of the original study. However, due to limited computational resources, we were unable to analyze the CLEF dataset, although the link was available. This limitation has been noted and will be included in the challenges encountered during the replication process.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Reproduction Results

The tables below illustrate the weighted accuracy percentages for different feature sets across various SVM cost factors ($\lambda = 1, 2, 3$) and F1 scores. The first shows the results for the Schwarz et al. dataset (table 1), while the second shows the results without standard scalars (table 2) and the third shows the results with standard scalars (table 3) for the Sondhi et al. dataset.

¹<https://github.com/MarcosFP97/Health-Rel>

Table 1. Comparison of results for Schwarz et al. dataset (deviating values were marked gray)

Features	SVM cost factor	F1	F1 (reliable class)	F1 (non-reliable class)	Weighted accuracy (%)		
					$\lambda = 1$	$\lambda = 2$	$\lambda = 3$
LINKS							
Paper Results	1	0.94	0.97	0	93.75	-	-
	2	0.94	0.97	0	-	88.26	-
	3	0.94	0.97	0	-	-	83.4
Our Results	1	0.94	0.97	0	93.75	-	-
	2	0.94	0.97	0	-	88.26	-
	3	0.94	0.97	0	-	-	83.4
LINKS + COMMERCIAL							
Paper Results	1	0.94	0.97	0	93.75	-	-
	2	0.94	0.97	0	-	88.26	-
	3	0.94	0.97	0	-	-	83.4
Our Results	1	0.94	0.97	0	93.75	-	-
	2	0.94	0.97	0	-	88.26	-
	3	0.94	0.97	0	-	-	83.4
WORDS (REMOVING STOPWORDS)							
Paper Results	1	0.93	0.96	0	92.5	-	-
	2	0.91	0.95	0.25	-	87.01	-
	3	0.91	0.95	0.33	-	-	85.42
Our Results	1	0.9	0.95	0	90	-	-
	2	0.9	0.95	0.25	-	85.83	-
	3	0.91	0.95	0.4	-	-	85.38
WORDS (KEEPING STOPWORDS)							
Paper Results	1	0.91	0.95	0	91.25	-	-
	2	0.91	0.95	0	-	85.88	-
	3	0.91	0.95	0.2	-	-	84.54
Our Results	1	0.91	0.95	0	91.25	-	-
	2	0.93	0.96	0.2	-	88.26	-
	3	0.93	0.96	0.2	-	-	84.54
ALL (REMOVING STOPWORDS)							
Paper Results	1	0.94	0.97	0	93.75	-	-
	2	0.91	0.95	0	-	85.88	-
	3	0.91	0.95	0	-	-	81.13
Our Results	1	0.9	0.95	0	90	-	-
	2	0.91	0.95	0.4	-	88.15	-
	3	0.91	0.95	0.4	-	-	85.38
ALL (KEEPING STOPWORDS)							
Paper Results	1	0.93	0.96	0	92.5	-	-
	2	0.91	0.95	0.25	-	87.02	-
	3	0.91	0.95	0.33	-	-	85.42
Our Results	1	0.91	0.95	0	91.25	-	-
	2	0.93	0.96	0.2	-	88.26	-
	3	0.93	0.96	0.2	-	-	84.54

Table 2. Comparison of results for Sondhi et al. dataset without Standard Scaler

Features	Our Results			Sondhi et al. original			Sondhi et al. Paper Results		
	Weighted accuracy (%)								
	$\lambda = 1$	$\lambda = 2$	$\lambda = 3$	$\lambda = 1$	$\lambda = 2$	$\lambda = 3$	$\lambda = 1$	$\lambda = 2$	$\lambda = 3$
Links	68.3	75.9	73.6	60.8	71.1	79.6	70.5	80.0	73.5
Links + Commercial	68.3	78.5	74.3	67.8	75.9	79.6	69.7	79.4	74.3
Words (removing stopwords)	71.4	73.2	75.0	–	–	–	80.8	80.2	80.3
Words (keeping stopwords)	73.6	77.2	82.1	80.6	83.9	85.0	82.8	85.6	88.5
All (removing stopwords)	98.9	98.5	98.8	–	–	–	97.5	98.3	98.6
All (keeping stopwords)	96.4	96.7	96.4	80.0	83.2	86.8	96.1	96.3	96.5

Table 3. Comparison of results for Sondhi et al. dataset with Standard Scaler

Features	Our Results			Sondhi et al. Paper Results		
	Weighted accuracy (%)					
	$\lambda = 1$	$\lambda = 2$	$\lambda = 3$	$\lambda = 1$	$\lambda = 2$	$\lambda = 3$
Links	73.6	77.6	77.2	74.4	78.1	76.4
Links + Commercial	70.8	77.4	78.6	73.3	76.5	79.9
Words (removing stopwords)	98.1	98.2	98.2	97.2	98.3	98.5
Words (keeping stopwords)	98.1	98.2	98.2	98.1	98.3	98.9
All (removing stopwords)	97.8	98.2	98.2	97.2	98.3	98.5
All (keeping stopwords)	98.1	98.2	98.2	97.8	98.3	98.9

3.2 Statistical Tests

In this report, we conducted statistical tests to analyze the differences between various sets of data obtained from different experimental conditions, with particular focus on comparing corresponding Lambda groups (compared values for $\lambda = 1$, $\lambda = 2$ and $\lambda = 3$ over all categories). The tests employed aimed to assess normality, homogeneity of variances, and significant differences between groups.

First, the normality of the individual data sets was checked using the Shapiro-Wilk test. The results showed that the data was not normally distributed in most cases. As a result, parametric tests that assume normality may not be appropriate.

Next, we examined the homogeneity of variances between our experimental results and the results reported in the study using Levene’s test. The results indicate that there are no significant differences in variance for the majority of comparisons, allowing for meaningful group comparisons.

Given the non-normal distribution of the data, we decided to use non-parametric tests to assess the differences between the groups. Specifically, we used the Mann-Whitney-U-Test, an alternative to the t-Test, which we used for the normally distributed data.

To summarize, with a significance level (α) set at 0.05, non-significant p-values above this threshold were consistently observed in all statistical tests, indicating no significant differences between the compared groups. This shows that the groups can be considered comparable despite the deviations from the normal distribution.

These results contribute to the robustness and reliability of the conclusions of the study and demonstrate the validity of the test results.

4 DISCUSSION

One of the strengths of the original study by Fernández-Pichel et al. lies in the documentation. The researchers have provided a comprehensive description of their experimental setup. The accessibility of the entire code base via a Git repository facilitates reproduction. The code is not only available, but also structured in such a way that it is easy to reproduce. The inclusion of a `build.sh` script and a `requirements.txt` file in the repository enables straightforward installation and execution of the code (see Table 4).

In addition, the inclusion of all data sets used in the study in the Git repository or through valid links to external sources contributes to transparency and replicability. The availability of the data is crucial for others to be able to repeat the experiments under the same conditions.

Table 4. Encountered Problems in Different Categories

Categories	✓ was the case, × was not
A. Code/Setup Difficulties	
1. Code not provided	×
2. Code partially not provided	×
3. Faulty code provided	×
4. Information about software versions missing	×
5. Specific hardware and software setup necessary	✓
B. Data	
1. Data not provided	×
2. Data partially not provided	✓ (only valid link to Data)
3. Metadata not provided	✓
C. Process	
1. Comparison metrics or baselines not discussed	×
2. Experimental setup not described	×
3. Experiment workflow incomplete	×
4. Inconsistencies in paper, code and data	×
5. Results differ significantly	×

4.1 Confirmation of Findings

Our replication efforts aimed to confirm the original paper’s findings on reliability prediction for health-related content. The comparison of results and statistical tests provided valuable insights into the replicability of the study. In general, our findings align with the original results, confirming the robustness of the reliability prediction model.

4.2 Impact on Results

Although we encountered limitations, the overall impact on the results remains consistent with the original conclusions. Our replication efforts shed light on the robustness of the results of the original study.

5 CONCLUSION

The aim of this replication attempt was to assess the replicability of the study by Fernández-Pichel et al. on the prediction of the reliability of health-related content. [1]. Our comprehensive investigation included replication of the trial design, procedures and results, as well as highlighting challenges encountered during the trial.

The results of our replication, presented in the form of statistical comparisons and tables, are generally consistent with the original results. Although we encountered limitations, such as the unavailability of specific hardware, which meant that not all datasets could be illuminated, our efforts confirm the robustness of the reliability prediction model proposed by Fernández-Pichel et al. The statistical tests performed show that the groups are comparable despite deviations from the normal distribution, which underpins the reliability of the study's conclusions.

This replication study underlines the importance of open and transparent practices in sharing code, data and experimental details to enable reliable scientific progress.

REFERENCES

- [1] Marcos Fernández-Pichel, David E. Losada, Juan C. Pichel, and David Elswailer. 2021. Reliability Prediction for Health-Related Content: A Replicability Study. In *Advances in Information Retrieval: 43rd European Conference on IR Research, ECIR 2021, Virtual Event, March 28 – April 1, 2021, Proceedings, Part II*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, 47–61. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72240-1_4
- [2] Jimmy, G. Zuccon, João Palotti, Lorraine Goeuriot, and Liadh Kelly. 2018. Overview of the CLEF 2018 Consumer Health Search Task. In *International Conference of the Cross- Language Evaluation Forum for European Languages*. Avignon, France. http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2125/invited_paper_17.pdf
- [3] Julia Schwarz and Meredith Morris. 2011. Augmenting web pages and search results to support credibility assessment. In *Proceedings of the 29th Annual SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (Vancouver, Canada, May 7 – 12, 2011)*. CHI '11. ACM, New York, 1245–1254. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1978942.1979127>
- [4] P. Sondhi, V. G. V. Vydiswaran, and C. Zhai. 2012. Reliability Prediction of Webpages in the Medical Domain. In *Baeza-Yates, R., et al. Advances in Information Retrieval. ECIR 2012. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 7224*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 219–231. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-28997-2_19